

Reducing food losses in Ghana's food systems and urban markets

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Background

Across the world, about 14% of all edible food produced, worth \$400 billion, is lost between harvest and retail each year¹. These losses represent a major inefficiency in global food systems, with far-reaching implications for food security, economic development, and the environment in both developed and developing countries. Reducing supply chain and post-harvest losses is said to have a triple benefit; a) for the climate, b) for food security, and c) for environmental sustainability.

In recognition of the scale and urgency of food losses/waste, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) under Target 12.3 call to halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels by 2030. The Agenda 2030 Sustainable Development Goal 12.3 also aimed at reducing food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest stages. Achieving this goal is step in the right direction, given the major inefficiencies in storage, handling, and market systems, with corresponding increase in losses from the farm level to post-harvest stages even before food reaches consumers in low income countries. Same can not be said for high income countries as most of losses/waste occurs at retail and consumption level (22.5%) of the supply chain².

Food loss is both an economic and social concern in Ghana and regions alike. The Chef for Change Ghana Foundation (CFGF) estimates that more than 35 percent of food goes uneaten each year, translating into an annual loss of about US \$8.9 billion. Aside the economic cost alone, food losses undermine the quest for national food security and intensify environmental pressures. For example, in 2024, a study by Food Security Information Network and Global Network Against Food Crisis, found that over 44.3 million people in West Africa and Sahel regions³ are acutely food insecure, while Food and Agriculture Organization found about two million people were acutely food insecure in Ghana between the period of June and August 2025⁴.

Sadly, however, the Northern and the transitional zones only accounts for 17% of Ghana's population but constitute 56% of all food insecure persons⁵. While global efforts to reduce food loss/waste continue to expand, Ghana must intensify its actions toward halving global per capita food waste and to meet food loss reduction of 25% target. This policy brief draws on findings from an independent market survey conducted in 2025 at the Tamale Aboabo Market, the largest trading hub in the Northern Region, to highlights how market-level inefficiencies, particularly in handling perishable crops such as tomatoes, translate into substantial food

losses and waste. We also examine how simple, context-driven interventions, could minimize losses while enhancing livelihoods for market traders and small-scale farmers. Local-level analysis such as this one is essential to bridge the gap between policy and practice. We reveal the economic, environmental, policy, social and health implications of food losses/waste, and in doing so, we provided a snapshot of how grassroots realities in a developing economy intersect with global food system challenges, and how targeted, low-cost solutions can drive measurable change in urban markets systems of Ghana. To sum up, we inadvertently revealed the hidden challenges and missed opportunities of food loss/waste.

Key findings and policy consideration

- Food loss in Ghana's local markets remains is a rarely talk about issue yet market level inefficiencies leads to a staggering loss on the supply chain. Once in every two weeks, each tomato traders lose more than a basket of produce valued at a cost of about GHS 500. A lot more needs to be done to improve this hidden but ongoing economic and environmental cost in urban markets of Ghana.
- There is increasing awareness of food loss as a development issue, but there exists limited institutional capacity to address it. Investment in infrastructure, training, and coordination have so far been low, particularly in urban markets where most perishable commodities are traded.
- Structural limitations such as inadequate cold storage facilities and poor transport logistics were found as major drivers of food losses. Produce often arrives at the market already damaged due to long travel times and exposure to heat. Affordable, small-scale cold storage systems could significantly reduce losses among traders.
- To address inherent losses within the Ghanaian urban markets and food systems, collaboration between traders, local authorities, and private actors is essential. Coordinated interventions can ensure that infrastructure investments, waste management, and value-chain improvements are aligned to reduce loss at multiple points.
- Value addition and processing remain underdeveloped despite strong potential to extend the shelf life of perishable produce. Establishing small-scale tomato processing units near major markets could absorb surplus produce during harvest peaks, create jobs, and improve food availability throughout the year.
- Training and awareness for traders are critical. Capacity-building programs on post-harvest handling, temperature management, and sorting techniques would strengthen local knowledge and reduce daily spoilage.
- Data collection and systematic monitoring are necessary to inform action. Establishing a simple, market-level system to quantify food losses would help identify trends, guide investment priorities, and measure progress over time.
- Although there are structural limitations, there is strong willingness among market traders to adopt better practices if given the means. Even small-scale, low-cost interventions such as shaded stalls, improved packaging, and transport coordination could go a long way to achieve measurable improvements in income and environmental outcomes.

¹ FAO. 2019. The State of Food and Agriculture 2019. Moving forward on food loss and waste reduction. Rome. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.

² Baykoca, B., Yilmaz, S (2025). Understanding food loss patterns across developed and developing countries using a GDP, growth rate, and health expenditure-based typology. *Sci Rep* 15, 27597. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-13156-3>

³ FSIN and Global Network Against Food Crises. 2024. GRFC 2024. Rome

⁴ [Two million people in Ghana faced acute food insecurity - Ghana Business News](#)

⁵ World food programme (2025). Annual Country Report. [Ghana | World Food Programme](#)

The underlying causes of food losses

Food losses in local markets are a silent but persistent threat to food security and environmental sustainability. In many developing regions, a significant portion of fresh produce never reaches consumers in edible condition. These losses often occur in the short journey between the farm and the market, a stage where inadequate storage, poor handling, and inefficient logistics converge.

At the Tamale Aboabo Market, one of the busiest trading centres in Northern Ghana, food loss has become part of daily market life. Perishable goods such as tomatoes, which form an essential part of local diets, are vulnerable. Same is true for edible fruits.

An independent market survey was conducted in 2025 to identify hidden challenges and the missed opportunities of food losses/waste among tomato traders. Surprisingly at the time of the survey, every tomato trader interviewed routinely sorted out spoiled produce before sale. On average, each vendor lost more than one basket of fresh tomatoes every two weeks, amounting to about ten baskets lost among five traders over the same period. Across all major markets in Ghana a basket of tomatoes is approximately value at 500 GHS. A cumulative lost of ten baskets would result in a staggering economic loss of about 5000 GHS.

Based on interviews with traders and observations at the site, we have identified five underlying causes of these losses:

- A major revelation is the inherent nature of the product. Tomatoes are highly perishable and sensitive to heat, moisture, and pressure. Even short exposure to direct sunlight or rough handling during transport can lead to bruising and rapid decay.
- Market and social dynamics. Many traders operate individually and without formal coordination, leading to market gluts during peak harvest seasons. With limited buyers and storage space, unsold produce often spoils within days.
- Infrastructure and logistical challenges. Poor road conditions delay transport from farmgate to market, while the absence of cold storage facilities accelerates deterioration. Produce frequently arrives already damaged or overripe.
- Financial and institutional constraints. High costs of cold storage, and limited access to credit restrict traders from investing in preservation or value addition technologies. Lamenting passionately, one respondent had this to say; *“I understand tomatoes are perishable food products, but the high cost of cold storage options coupled with delayed transport from the farmgate leads to rapid spoilage, especially during the hot season.”* – Tomato Vendor, Tamale Aboabo Market (2025)
- Behavioral and awareness factors. Though many participants demonstrated awareness of the losses incurred, handling practices are often based on tradition rather than training. Most traders lack technical knowledge on temperature management, packaging, or early sorting to prevent spread of rot.

It is however saddening to note that these losses rarely end up quietly. Spoiled/sorted tomatoes and other perishables are often transported to nearby dumping sites or landfills, where they decompose, producing foul odours and releasing methane emissions a potent greenhouse gas that contributes to climate change. This pattern reflects a broader national concern: food waste has become one of the dominant components of urban solid waste in Ghana. The situation in Aboabo reveals how market-level inefficiencies intersect with broader sustainability goals. Each spoiled basket represents transcends beyond financial loss for traders to a missed opportunity to strengthen food security and reduce environmental impact.

Sorted tomatoes at Tamale Aboabo Market
Photo by Safianu Chakilia

Opening this conversation is therefore essential: addressing food loss at the market level offers one of the most immediate, practical, and impactful pathways to improving livelihoods, reducing waste, and advancing Ghana's progress toward **SDG 12.3**.

Do food losses mean anything to us?

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Goal 12 which states “Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns” under target 12.3 was set to reduce food losses along supply chain and to halve food wastage by 2030. This requires Ghana's commitment to this course as a member state. Therefore, if this is anything to go by, then the findings presented herein reflect how small-scale inefficiencies can accumulate into significant economic, environmental, and social challenges. While the losses observed may appear localized, their implications extend far beyond the market, affecting livelihoods, public health, and the sustainability of food systems in Northern Ghana.

Economic Implications

The economic cost of food loss/waste is a well-known fact. Tomato losses directly erode the incomes of traders and farmers, particularly women, who dominate retail activities in the market. Each tomato lost/wasted represents a financial setback, in an already low-margin business environment. Cumulatively, these losses reduce household earnings, undermine market stability, and weaken incentives for smallholder production. For the wider economy, persistent losses translate into reduced availability of affordable food and inefficiencies in the agricultural value chain.

Environmental implications

Almost all food waste ends up at landfill sites and constitutes the largest components of solid waste in Ghana. When such waste is disposed of at open dumpsites, they decompose and release methane, a potent greenhouse gas which contributes to climate change. Similarly, foul odors from decomposed waste aggravates local air quality which in turns affect respiratory disorders. The absence of state-of-the-art waste facility in the region means that most spoiled produce ends up mixed with general waste, increasing the environmental footprint of market operations.

Social and Public health implications

The high rate of food loss also has social costs. Reduced availability of fresh produce limits access to nutritious food for high-income households and those with means to afford them. At the same time, unsanitary disposal practices expose traders and consumers to health risks from decaying waste and contaminated surroundings. In effect this undermines both livelihoods and community well-being.

Policy Relevance

From the policy perspective, addressing food losses at Aboabo Market is not only a matter of improving market efficiency, it is also a development and environmental priority. The issue links directly to Ghana's commitments under SDG 12.3 on sustainable consumption and production. Reducing losses would enhance food security, lower waste management costs, and contribute to climate change mitigation efforts. As such, the problem demands coordinated policy attention that combines infrastructure investment, trader capacity building, and integration of market-level interventions into broader municipal and national food strategies.

How Can We Reduce Food Losses in Ghana's Food Systems and Urban Markets?

Across Ghana, and many other countries, there is growing recognition of the need to reduce food losses along the supply chain and intensified effort to achieve food security. National programmes, private initiatives, and civil-society organizations are increasingly working to build awareness, improve handling practices, and strengthen collaboration between producers, traders, and policy actors. To better understand local realities of food loss in urban markets, we conducted a survey at Tamale's Aboabo Market in 2025, engaging traders to identify practical measures that could limit food losses and improve food security in the northern region. Based on the discussions held with traders, we have explored potential solution areas and emerging practices to address the underlying challenges identified.

Initiatives Targeted at Market Systems

- **Improving storage and infrastructure** remains central. Introduction of small, solar-powered cold rooms and better-ventilated stalls could slow ripening and protect produce during periods of high temperature. Simple shading and packaging innovations, adapted to local market conditions, can also make a measurable difference.
- **Enhancing coordination between farmers and traders** can balance supply and demand. When farmers receive timely market information on prices and volumes, they are less likely to flood urban markets with perishable produce during peak harvest periods. Mobile-based communication platforms could facilitate this exchange.

Both measures require a policy framework that encourages investment in market infrastructure and supports communication across the value chain. Partnerships between local authorities, development agencies, and the private sector can ensure that facilities are maintained and information flows remain active in the supply chain.

Solutions Within the Urban Food Chain

- **Developing small-scale processing and value-addition enterprises** offers a direct way to reduce loss and create employment. Converting fresh tomatoes into paste, puree, or dried products extends shelf life and diversifies market opportunities.
- **Encouraging fair and transparent trading practices** can protect vendors from last-minute cancellations and delayed payments, which often lead to unsold or spoiled goods. Stronger market management guidelines and enforcement can reduce uncertainty and waste.

These approaches demonstrate that structural improvements in local food chains can yield both economic and social benefits. By linking farmers, traders, and processors, Ghana can create more resilient market ecosystems that better withstand supply fluctuations.

Opportunities for Wider Impact

- **Educational programmes and public awareness campaigns** should emphasize the value of minimizing food loss from harvest to retail. Integrating food-loss reduction into agricultural training and extension services can foster behavioural change and long-term improvements in handling practices.
- **Promoting circular-economy initiatives**, such as composting unsold produce or using organic waste for animal feed and bioenergy would reduce the environmental footprint of urban markets and contribute to cleaner cities. Efforts in these areas should be guided by reliable data and continuous collaboration among stakeholders.

This policy brief is based on a 2025 market survey on food losses conducted at the Tamale Aboabo Market in Northern Ghana by Safianu Chakilia, with research support from Maxwell Anamdare Asale. We acknowledge the cooperation of tomato traders at the Tamale Aboabo Market, whose participation in the surveys made this study possible.